

LONG-TERM PERFORMANCE OF A COMPOSITE TRUSS BRIDGE AFTER 25 YEARS IN SERVICE

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ABSTRACT

After 25 years of service in a harsh Alpine climate, the Pontresina pedestrian bridge was subjected to a third inspection and assessment of serviceability, structural safety, and durability. The assessment included a full-scull static serviceability loading, investigations of coupons taken from an extracted transverse beam, and visual inspection. The mid-span deflections did not exhibit any notable changes compared to the results of the previous inspections. Similarly, the elastic modulus obtained from coupons remained unchanged. However, the strength continued to decrease to approximately 69% of the initial value, but the decrease now almost leveled off. The visual inspection showed an increase in fiber blooming on the surfaces exposed to direct sunlight and initiation and propagation of local cracks due to inappropriate storage and lifting. Structural safety and serviceability are however still not affected by the strength reduction and these local damages.

KEYWORDS

Glass fiber-polymer composites; Full-scull testing; Material degradation; Inspection; Durability.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber-polymer composites are increasingly being used in civil engineering structures as an alternative to traditional materials (steel, reinforced concrete, etc.), due to their high strength-to-weight ratio, excellent chemical and fatigue resistance, and ease of installation. Pultruded profiles, glass pultrusions in particular, are most commonly used in new constructions (Siwowski et al., 2018), such as truss bridges (Keller et al., 2007) and bridge decks (Keller et al., 2014), which were first put into service in the 1980s. Despite the advantages of fiber-polymer composites, there are still concerns about their long-term performance and durability under service loads and environmental factors, such as moisture, temperature, and Ultraviolet (UV) radiation, due to the relatively short experience with these composite structures. Long-term monitoring and periodic visual inspections can be conducted to better address these concerns. For example, an assessment of the Tech 21 all-composite bridge after 8 years of service was performed and indicated that no visible structural degradation and damage on the surface of structural members were observed (Farhey, 2005). Similarly, the Aberfeldy footbridge showed no significant degradation in performance after 20 years of service, although repairs were needed due to damage caused by impact loads and fiber blooming (Stratford, 2012). Loading tests and visual inspections were also carried out on a composite slab bridge (Alampalli, 2006) and the West Mill Bridge (Lee, 2012) after 4 and 8 years of service, respectively. However, in all these cases, the long-term behavior of the composite structures was not thoroughly studied and the observation period was relatively short.

In this study, the results of the third periodic inspection of the Pontresina bridge after 25 years of service are presented, which is a continuous work of the previous assessments in 2005 (after 8 years) (Keller et al., 2007) and 2014 (after 17 years) (Keller et al., 2016). Similar to the previous inspections, a full-scull static loading was performed to assess the structural serviceability, investigations of coupons taken from an extracted transverse beam to evaluate the material degradation and visual inspection was carried out

to identify local changes and structural damage. The findings are compared to the results of the previous inspections.

DESCRIPTION OF PONTRESINA BRIDGE

The Pontresina bridge was installed over Flaz Creek in Pontresina, Switzerland, 1997. It is located in the Swiss Alps at an altitude of 1790 m and exposed to harsh Alpine climatic conditions. It is one of the first full-composite pedestrian bridges in Europe, as shown in Figure 1. The bridge is only used during the winter for ski touring and removed to the bank side in the spring due to high water. The truss bridge consists of two spans of 2×12.5 m with a total width of 1.93 m (including a walkway of 1.50 m) and a depth of 1.48 m. Each span weighs 16.5 kN and can easily be installed and removed using a helicopter. The joints in one span are bolted and in the other span adhesively bonded, with additional bolts as back up in case of adhesive connection failure. Pultruded glass composite profiles were used to assemble the bridge, which consist of glass fibers impregnated by an isophthalic polyester resin. The fiber architecture comprised mainly unidirectional rovings in the center and one or two outer combined mats towards the surfaces. Veil layers were applied during pultrusion to improve durability. More details about the structural concept and properties of the pultruded profiles could be found in (Keller et al., 2007)(Keller et al., 2016).

Figure 1: Pontresina bridge (2023)

FULL-SCALE STATIC LOADING

Figure 2: Full-scale static loading on the bonded span of Pontresina bridge.

The full-scale static loading of both spans was performed in 2022 at EPFL, Switzerland, as performed before the installation in 1997, and repeated in 2005 (Keller et al., 2007) and 2014 (Keller et al., 2016). A serviceability load of approximately 4 kN/m^2 (pedestrian load) and 10 kN (maintenance vehicle) was

applied to each span using ten pallets of bricks weighing 8.4 kN each, as shown in Figure 2. The pallets were applied following the same sequence as in the previous inspections, as indicated in Figure 2. The deflections at specified locations of each girder were measured for each load step.

The resulting midspan load-deflection curves (average deflections from each span) for both bonded and bolted spans are shown in Figure 3, which are compared to the previous results obtained in 1997, 2005 and 2014. The stiffness of the bonded and bolted spans did not notably change between 1997 and 2022 if taking into account that (i) the 1997 experiments were performed in a different lab, (ii) the weights, dimensions and exact locations of the brick pallets on the bridge slightly varied, and (iii) the measurement systems were also different.

Figure 3: Load-deflection curves in the midspan of both spans of Pontresian bridge measured in 1997, 2005, 2014 and 2022.

COUPON TESTS

As conducted in 2005 and 2014, a transverse beam of the bolted span was replaced by a new one to examine the effect of the environmental conditions on the degradation of the tensile modulus and strength after 25 years of service. The top surface of the upper flange of the transverse beam exhibited significant fiber blooming, however, no visible cracks were detected. Five longitudinal coupons (300 × 25 × 8 mm³) were extracted from the upper and bottom flanges, and web each. Strain gauges were glued to both sides of the specimens to measure the strain during loading. The specimens were loaded at a displacement rate of 5 mm/min until ultimate failure.

Figure 4: Failure modes of coupons from the bottom flange (side view).

The failure mode exhibited predominantly fiber explosion within the gauge length, accompanied by some delamination near the tab between fiber rovings and outer mat layers, as shown in Figure 4; the failure mode did not show any changes when compared to the results of previous inspections.

The normalized axial tensile modulus and strength of the composite coupons from upper flange versus the ages are shown in Figure 5, which were obtained from different years and normalized by dividing them by the average initial values obtained in 1997. The results showed that the tensile modulus did not show a significant decrease over 25 years. The tensile strength however exhibited a significant decrease during the 25 years, which was fitted by the power law relationship. On average, the strength decreased to 79% of its initial value after 8 years (measured in 2005), further reduced to 71% and 69% after 17 (in 2014) and 25 years (in 2022). However, the decrease now almost leveled off.

Figure 5: Normalized tensile modulus and strength versus ages of composite coupons with fitted curves.

VISUAL INSPECTION

Surface color

The surface color changed in 2005 (Keller et al., 2007) from the initial total white color (RAL9016) to yellow-white (RAL1015). However, the color did not show a significant change in the following inspections and is still a yellow-white (RAL1015) in 2022, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Comparison of surface color between exposed and unexposed profiles after 25 years.

Fiber blooming

Fiber blooming was observed in all three inspections. To better characterize the extent of fiber blooming, four levels were defined, as described in Table 1 (Keller et al., 2016). In 2005, several local fiber blooming areas of level 2 were observed on the top surface of the upper chords and transverse

beams due to direct sunlight exposure. Fiber blooming had greatly increased for the entire bridge by 2014; some small areas of level 3 appeared on the surface of the upper chords and transverse beams, and level 2 and level 1 blooming initiated on the diagonal and vertical profiles, respectively. It should be noted that the upper chords were painted after the 2014 inspection since the upper chord also serves as a handrail for the users. The fiber blooming area continued to increase significantly by 2022 in the unpainted parts. Level 2 and 3 blooming was further increased on the transverse beam, while level 1 and level 2 showed greater increases on the diagonals, as shown in Figure 7, and the vertical surfaces exhibited a smaller increase.

Table 1: Levels of fiber blooming

Level	Description
0	Shiny and intact surface (no fiber blooming)
1	Mat and slightly rough surface (pattern of black dots)
2	Exposed fibers of the outer mat layer
3	Exposed fibers of deeper UD rovings

Figure 7: Fiber blooming on top surface of diagonal profile.

Cracks in profile flanges

Several local cracks were already detected at flange-web junctions along the profiles (parallel to the rovings) of the upper and bottom chords, as well as small cracks in the top flanges of the transverse beams, in the first inspection (2005). These cracks were caused by the inappropriate storage of the bridge on the banks during spring and impacts from lifting the bridge, while the cracks in the top flanges of the transverse beams mainly resulted from the annual removal of the deck grating. Crack maps were created during the second inspection (2014) to record the location and length of these cracks, as shown in Figure 8 for cracks observed in the upper chords of the bonded span. The blue and red lines represent the cracks observed in 2014 and 2022, respectively. There was no significant increase in the number or length of the cracks between 2014 and 2022.

Figure 8: Longitudinal cracks in the upper chord observed in 2014 and 2022 of bonded spans (bottom view on bottom flanges).

Figure 9: Representative longitudinal crack in the flange of the bottom chord (bottom view).

The conclusion already drawn earlier was confirmed that closed sections should have been used at these locations and not open sections with free flanges sensitive to impact and transverse bending. Since the cracks are always in the profile direction, they do not notably affect stiffness and strength.

CONCLUSIONS

The third periodic evaluation of the serviceability, structural safety, and durability of the Pontresina bridge after 25 years of service was performed in 2022. A full-scale static serviceability loading of the bridge and investigations of coupons from an extracted beam were conducted, and fiber blooming and crack development in the profiles were identified. The conclusions of this work are summarized as follows:

- (1) The stiffness of the bonded and bolted span exhibited no significant changes compared to previous inspections, which showed that the structural serviceability did not change over the 25 years.
- (2) The tensile modulus obtained from coupons also remained unchanged throughout 25 years. The strength decreased to approximately 69% of the initial value, however, the rate of decrease has now almost leveled off.
- (3) The extent of the fiber blooming was further increased, however, no significant increase in the number or length of the cracks was observed between 2014 and 2022. As a result, the global structural behavior remains not affected by these damages.

CITATIONS

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.